

The role of vocational education and training for empowering NEETs: Cedefop insights

- *Cedefop experts*
- Q&A

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Youth in education, youth in employment: Boosting European policies for social inclusion

18th Cedefop Brussels seminar, 23 June 2025, 10.00 -13.30 CET, Brussels

#CedefopBrusselsSeminar

8 million young people in Europe are NEETs

The size of an EU member state

In your opinion, why are NEETs an important policy issue?

Are you directly involved in supporting NEETs?

Are you aware of initiatives targeting NEETs?

In your opinion, how could NEETs be best supported?

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Decreasing rates of NEETs but persisting challenges

8 million NEETs in the EU in 2024

- Overall economic development since 2009 crisis

- Targeted Member states interventions

- Support by EU policy framework

Source: Eurostat, LFS, 2024

EU policy framework supporting NEETs

- **2013** Youth Guarantee Council Recommendation
- **2014** Youth Guarantee Implementation Plans
- **2016** Skills Agenda
- **2017** European Pillar of Social Rights Declaration
- **2020** Reinforced Youth Guarantee and updated Youth Guarantee Implementation Plans
- **2020** New European Skills agenda – Pact for Skills
- **2020** Council Recommendation on VET
- **2020** Osnabrück Declaration
- **2021** European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan
- **2021-2027** European Social Fund Plus (ESF+)
- **2021** ALMA (Aim, Learn, Master, Achieve)
- **2025** Union of Skills
- **2025** Forthcoming Herning Declaration

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Progress made towards the EU target

- EU strategic objective: **NEET rate 9% by 2030**
- **Nine (9)** Member states have already met this goal
- **Five (5)** are close to achieving the target: currently below 10%
- **Eight (8)** are far from reaching it: currently above 12%

Young people (aged 15-29) neither in employment nor in education and training 2024 (%)

Source: Eurostat, LFS, 2024

Gender gap in NEETs rates

**12.1% NEETs are women
vs. 10% men in 2024**

Source: Eurostat, LFS, 2024

→ **Notable gender disparities
within member states**

→ **Inverted picture in five (5)
Member States**

Regional inequalities: Remote NEETs at greater risk

10%

Cities

11.4%

**Towns &
suburbs**

12.3%

**Rural
areas**

- Significant rural-urban disparities
- In some Member States this divide is above 10 percentage points
- Rural areas often face structural disadvantages

Cedefop's work on NEETs and inclusion

Carrying out research to address data gaps and inform policy

Promoting peer learning through policy learning fora

Developing VET tools for policy makers and practitioners

Leveraging a pan European network of ambassadors for inclusion

Cedefop knowledge hub on inclusion

VET toolkit for tackling early leaving

www.cedefop.europa.eu/TEL-toolkit

VET toolkit for empowering NEETs

www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/tools/neets

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From early leaver to NEET

Young people who left education and training and combine multiple disadvantage, possibly facing health and psycho-social issues

Young people not in employment, education or training (NEETs)

VET toolkit for empowering NEETs

Source of support to young people not in employment, education or training

Young people not in employment, education or training (NEETs)

Distance from participation in employment, education and training

SEEKING WORK AND/OR EDUCATION OR TRAINING

NOT SEEKING WORK AND/OR EDUCATION OR TRAINING

Re-entrants

NEETs in recent search

NEETs in long-term search

Unavailable due to family responsibilities

Unavailable due to illness or disability

Discouraged and disengaged young people

SEEKING WORK AND/OR EDUCATION OR TRAINING

NOT SEEKING WORK AND/OR EDUCATION OR TRAINING

Re-entrants

NEETs in recent search

NEETs in long-term search

Unavailable due to family responsibilities

Unavailable due to illness or disability

Discouraged and disengaged young people

Re-entrants

Maria has signed a contract with a company and will begin her new job in 2 months. She is therefore not seeking another job opportunity or education programme as she believes that nothing could fit in terms of advancing her skills or earning work experience during this period of 2 months.

Young people who will soon re-enter employment and/or education or training.

Related intervention approaches

Lifelong guidance: supporting NEETs to manage their careers

Skills development

Distance from participation in employment, education and training

SEEKING WORK AND/OR EDUCATION OR TRAINING

NOT SEEKING WORK AND/OR EDUCATION OR TRAINING

Re-entrants

NEETs in recent search

NEETs in long-term search

Unavailable due to family responsibilities

Unavailable due to illness or disability

Discouraged and disengaged young people

Discouraged and disengaged young people

Nick completed secondary education several years ago and since then he has been inactive in terms of employment and continuing education. He believes that his qualifications are not enough to apply for an education programme to advance his skills and he is not seeking work as he does not think he is competitive enough to enter education and/or job market.

NEETs who are not seeking work or education or training because they believe that there are no job or education or training opportunities for them.

Related intervention approaches

Outreach

Lifelong guidance:
supporting NEETs to
manage their careers

Improving the appeal of
VET

Flexible and permeable
education and training
systems

Validation of non-formal
and informal learning

Feedback

VET toolkit for empowering NEETs

Source of support to young people not in employment, education or training

Introduction

Identify

Intervene

Evaluate

Resources

Advanced search

About the toolkit

Contact us

BLOG HIGHLIGHTS

27 APR 2021

What is the VET Toolkit for empowering NEETs?

This Europe-wide toolkit is inspired by successful VET practices and aims at helping policy makers, practitioners, and providers of support to young people not in employment, education, or training (NEETs) to design policies and implement practices that will better address the needs of NEETs, helping them to reintegrate into education or training and the labour market.

[VIEW ALL](#)

BROWSE BY

Type of resource

4
Tools

95
Publications

5
Statistics and data

30
Good practices

WAYS TO

Take part

- Evaluation plan for policy makers
- Evaluation plan for learning providers
- Become an ambassador tackling early leaving from VET

VET toolkit for empowering NEETs

Source of support to young people not in employment, education or training

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Intervene

Easing transitions into work

Show related risk factors

Flexible and permeable education and training systems

Show related risk factors

Helping female NEETs (re)integrate into education, employment or training

Improving the appeal of VET

Show related risk factors

Lifelong guidance: supporting NEETs to manage their careers

Show related risk factors

NEETs living in remote areas - Bridging the geographic divide

Show related risk factors

Offering mentorship programmes to NEETs

Show related risk factors

Outreach

Show related risk factors

Preparing NEETs to access green jobs

Skills development

Show related risk factors

Validation of non-formal and informal learning

Show related risk factors

Helping female NEETs

Comprehensive support for (re)entering employment, education and training

MENTORING

Provide support, guidance and growth opportunities

SKILLS VALIDATION

Opportunities for upskilling and reskilling

Rural NEETS

Bridging the geographic divide

Skills for the green transition and NEETs

Unlocking the potential of the circular economy

Micro-credentials

Supporting NEETs transitions into work

VET toolkit for empowering NEETs

Source of support to young people not in employment, education or training

🏠 Introduction

🔍 Identify

👤 Intervene

📄 Evaluate

🔧 Resources

🔍 Advanced search

👁 About the toolkit

✉ Contact us

Evaluate

- 1** Decide what to monitor and evaluate
- 2** Choose relevant indicators
- 3** Assess whether a programme or policy makes a difference
- 4** Decide if a programme or policy is good enough

Check our tools:

Evaluation plan for policy makers

Evaluation plan for learning providers

Ambassadors for inclusion

Cedefop research

Supporting evidence-based policy-making

Addressing data and research gaps

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Preventing and supporting NEETs

Leaving education early:
putting vocational education
and training centre stage

Volume I: investigating causes and extent

Leaving education early:
putting vocational education
and training centre stage

Volume II: evaluating policy impact

Cedefop policy messages

BRIEFING NOTE

Keeping young people in (vocational) education: what works?

Too many young people leave education (education) too soon. Yet early leavers are at high unemployment, poverty and crime, and now economy 1.25% of GDP. Can this flow be staunch

Who are the early leavers? As they stand, early leaving rates across the EU are not strictly comparable. Inconsistent country. An employer considered an employee. In some vocational dropouts programme. Not all countries end compulsory education at the same age; this varies between 15 and 18. For international comparisons, national statistics follow the Eurostat definition (18 to 24 year-olds who have completed only ISCED levels 2 and 3C, have no other qualifications, and have not been in education and training within the past four weeks). But concepts of vocational education and training are not strictly comparable.

BRIEFING NOTE

Vocational education and training prevent and counteracts early leaving from the education system

New findings shed light on the role vocational education and training play in attracting, retaining and reintegrating young people with different abilities and learning backgrounds

It is well known that young people facing learning difficulty or failure, or belonging to vulnerable groups, such as migrants, are often pointed towards vocational education and training (VET) pathways. These include programmes for low performers and for pupils who prefer non-academic learning; they offer many young people a (second) chance to obtain a labour-market-relevant qualification (1).

Much less is known, however, about young leavers' individual trajectories. What type of education/training programme have they left? Why? How many of them return to education? How many chose vocational education and training as a second chance option? And how many graduate eventually? So far, European statistics have only allowed for a quantification of the overall phenomenon, neither distinguishing between early leaving from general and from vocational education, nor breaking early leavers down into categories (2). To close these gaps, Cedefop launched a four-year project in 2013, analysing secondary data from the OECD's programme for the international assessment of adult competences (PIAAC) and Eurostat's labour force and adult education surveys, as well as primary data collected from selected countries (3). The results of the project are expected to provide a more differentiated basis for policy-making in prevention, intervention or compensatory measures to address early leaving from education and training.

provide a more differentiated basis for policy-making in prevention, intervention or compensatory measures to address early leaving from education and training.

Box 1. Tackling early leaving from education and training in Europe: strategies, policies and measures

More evidence – New insights

Vocational education and training programmes accommodate large numbers of returning learners who make a second education choice because they have either dropped out of (general) vocational education or decided to change learning pathway, often end up in vocational education and training. One third of those who have experienced dropout at upper secondary level subsequently take up a vocational training programme and ultimately obtain an upper or even post-secondary level qualification.

- (1) Keeping young people in (vocational) education: what works? Cedefop briefing note, No 9084, December 2013.
- (2) Meaningful categories of early leavers could be: non-starters (who have never taken up upper secondary VET), dropouts (who failed to complete a programme), and non-qualified learners (who have completed a programme without obtaining a qualification).
- (3) The first year of this research was coordinated with Eurycide's work on early leaving from school and led to the publication of a joint report in autumn 2014: Tackling early leaving from education and training: strategies, policies and measures (Box 1).

BRIEFING NOTE

PREVENTING LOW SKILLS THROUGH LIFELONG LEARNING

Flexible learning pathways to keep youth at risk and low-skilled adults in education or work

In 2017, 15.7% of low-qualified aged 15 to 29 were not in training (NEET), compare educated peers. In the same rate of low-qualified adults stood at 13.9% in the EU; qualified peers was at 4.2%

Low skills, usually associated with economic cost. They are individuals concerned, their earnings, self-confidence, and in civil society (4). This is why it has increasingly been the focus of early intervention, from offering low-skilled people and various upskilling in skills training.

BRIEFING NOTE

MAINSTREAMING VET POLICIES ADDRESSING EARLY LEAVING FROM EDUCATION AND TRAINING

From projects and local initiatives to national programmes and policies

In 2014, the rate of early leaving from education and training in the EU had dropped to just one percentage point above the Europe 2020 benchmark of less than 10%. This encouraging trend is partly owed to the numerous projects and initiatives across Europe over the last three decades which have supported young people at risk of dropping out of education. Yet many of these initiatives have neither aroused attention nor found a market beyond their local context, in spite of their success. What has prevented policy makers and practitioners in other places reaping their benefits? What does it take to transfer successful practices and make them work in different settings?

A persistent challenge: obtaining conclusive evaluations

Evaluations of the effectiveness of policies addressing early leaving from VET are scarce in Europe. When they are carried out they often convey only a partial understanding of whether and why a given policy worked and of the benefits it offered to individual learners.

Cedefop has mapped over 300 different initiatives conducted in 36 European countries (5). Evidence of success is available for only 44 of these. Some have not been evaluated but underpinned by monitoring data providing some clues as to the number of participants and, at best, their pathways. Evaluations of the whole range of indicators showing the ultimate effect of a policy on retention and qualification attainment, which can serve to inform policy making, are more an exception than the rule. There is a need to promote an evaluation culture to build capacity enabling policy learning.

Following analysis of the causes and manifestations of early leaving from education and training, and of policies preventing and counteracting the phenomenon (6), Cedefop has been looking at the conditions for mainstreaming successful projects and initiatives into regional/national programmes and for policy learning from one country to another. In its study on The role of VET in reducing early leaving from education and training (7), it has analysed numerous initiatives and policies, which have proven efficient in mitigating or eliminating early leaving risk factors, and identified their common key features.

Discover Cedefop's tools Cedefop's VET toolkit for which policy-makers can design, implement and evaluate Cedefop's resources for general and policy-makers working on usage of labour practices; and training on how to use them

- (4) All data from Eurostat: ec.europa.eu/eurostat
- (5) Low-qualified are individuals schooling corresponding to it they are compared to peers of Cedefop (2017). Interview in social cost of low-qualified adults

BRIEFING NOTE

VOCATIONAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING AS A LIFE JACKET

Cedefop's work on VET supporting social inclusion of young NEETs

Young people not in employment, education or training (NEETs) are absent both from the labour market and the education sector, thus facing a high risk of professional, digital and social exclusion. Analyses of the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic show that, in spite of EU countries' bold response to this crisis protecting jobs, businesses and livelihoods, yet again, young people were hardest hit by its effects. This is why young NEETs have continued to be a top policy priority at national and EU levels.

YOUNG NEETs: WHO ARE THEY?

In the EU, young people with no or low qualifications are, on average, three times more likely to be NEETs than those with tertiary education; and twice as likely as those with secondary education. Other factors also play a role: living in a household with low income, being raised by a single parent, living in a rural area, being born in a country outside the EU, or having a disability. Young NEETs often suffer from poverty, social exclusion, insecurity, or health problems (8).

Beyond personal circumstances, labour market failures and mismatches often disproportionately affect young people. The results of a 2020 large-scale research project in Greece, funded by the European Economic Area, illustrate the dire employment situation of young Greeks: 15.9% were unemployed and actively looking

for a job, compared to 6.3% of their peers in the EU as a whole (9). The large number of young unemployed in Greece includes many well-qualified young people. Perceiving vocational education and training (VET) as a potential route to a job, many of them are willing to attend a training programme, provided it will help them (re)enter the labour market.

VET TO EMPOWER YOUNG PEOPLE

In line with the principles of the European Pillar of Social Rights, VET, offering young people practical opportunities to obtain skills and acquire a qualification, is a powerful shield against marginalisation. According to the 2021 Council Resolution on a European education area by 2030, we are witnessing an increase in labour market needs for a different mix of skills and qualifications. Being closely tied to the labour market, VET can react swiftly to skill needs as they emerge. For example, to keep pace with the digitalisation of the European economy, VET is incorporating a range of digital skills, responding both to occupation-specific and transversal skill needs. It is also central to policies supporting young NEETs, such as outreach, personalised guidance, and assessment and validation of their existing formal and informal skills. It is the role of policy-makers to ensure VET's labour market relevance and so help unlock its inclusive potential. VET programmes, with their practical component, can help young people acquire entrepreneurship skills and ease their transition to work. Ultimately, they can provide young people with skills harnessing their employability and fostering their inclusion in society.

(8) Broken down by gender, this corresponds to 14.6% of men and 17.4% of women aged 20-34 for Greece, compared to 6.8% of men and 5.8% of women of that age for the EU as a whole.

Cedefop empowering VET teachers & trainers to promote inclusion

Research paper

Teachers and trainers in a changing world

Building up competences for inclusive, green and digitalised vocational education and training (VET)
Synthesis report

EMPOWERING TEACHERS AND TRAINERS TO MANAGE CHANGE

VET teacher and trainer professional development is crucial to helping them perform their many tasks

Teachers and trainers are at the forefront of initial vocational education and training (VET) delivery (1). In the face of the unprecedented challenges created by the pandemic and the war in Ukraine, their commitment and creativity have been central to sustaining teaching and learning in schools and workplaces. They play a key role in empowering young people, on whose lives and hopes the lockdowns have taken a particularly high toll, and in helping integrate refugees into Europe's labour markets.

Source: Cedefop.

The vocational training and labour market inclusion of young people not in employment, education or training (NEETs), of refugees, asylum seekers and other vulnerable groups has become a major focus. Today it is a cornerstone of high-quality VET², requiring specific psychosocial and intercultural skills from teachers and trainers.

- While a few countries do not specifically define VET as opposed to continuing VET (e.g. Ireland, Poland, Slovakia), most consider it as a distinct pathway to a qualification and occupation providing young people an access route to the labour market.
- The 2020 Chebrievka Declaration states that 'excellent and inclusive European VET are equally necessary for the competitiveness of European enterprises and a well-functioning European labour market', highlighting that they are in fact the two sides of the same coin.

At the same time, the greening of European economies and the rapid digitalisation of many jobs, including the teaching profession itself, confront them with more new skills requirements. This is why it is now more important than ever for them to upgrade and update their own skills to be able, in turn, to instil (self-)confidence in their students, trainees and apprentices, as well as offering them up-to-date knowledge and skills. This briefing note presents new evidence gathered by Cedefop on teacher and trainer initial training and continuous professional development (CPD), including many practical examples (3).

TEACHERS AND TRAINERS: DIFFERENT PROFILES AND QUALIFICATION NEEDS

The professionals who teach and train learners in initial VET can generally be distinguished by where and how they perform their tasks:

- staff teaching general subjects in VET schools;
- staff teaching VET-related subjects in VET schools. These comprise a theoretical part taught in classrooms and a practical one, taught in workshops;
- trainers teaching at workplaces.

Different qualifications are required for these distinct groups of professionals, who also need a tailored mix of skills to perform their tasks efficiently.

TEACHER AND TRAINER PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

All European countries have legal or other provisions that govern the professional status, work and CPD of VET school teachers and, to a lesser degree, trainers in workplaces.

(3) It is based on country reports on Teachers and trainers in a changing world by Cedefop's national Benchmark partners, available in the *Benchmark thematic presentation* collection and a forthcoming synthesis report prepared by Cedefop.

RESEARCH PAPER

No 47

Vocational pedagogies and benefits for learners: practices and challenges in Europe

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT FOR VET TEACHERS AND TRAINERS

A guarantee of quality in vocational education and training

Committed and competent teachers and trainers are crucial to ensuring the quality and labour market relevance of learning, both in VET schools/centres and in companies, and whether in classrooms, in workshops, in labs and simulated learning environments, or at the workplace. Teachers and trainers are responsible for strengthening the links between education and work, establishing new curricula, providing more, and high-quality, apprenticeships and other forms of work-based learning, and applying the European tools. In the coming years, VET teachers and trainers will be required to help shape quick and flexible responses to emerging needs, related both to the integration of thousands of refugees and migrants into the labour market and to the need to develop basic, digital and entrepreneurial skills. Providing teachers and trainers with access to quality professional development and support is essential to ensuring that both their technical competences and pedagogical skills are up to the highest standards.

While VET teacher and trainer professional development has been on the EU education policy agenda for many years (1), it has not been sufficiently visible in national policies (2). The Riga conclusions (2015) have put renewed emphasis on the issue, calling for systematic approaches to and opportunities for initial and continuing professional development (CPD) of VET teachers, trainers and mentors. Cooperation and partnerships among stakeholders are seen as a way to support this.

- (1) The *Europe's communication* (2010) had invited Member States to invest in and improve initial and continuing training for VET teachers and trainers by offering flexible training provision enabling them to:
- acquire the right set of competences;
 - take up broader and more complex training-related tasks;
 - deal with the increasing heterogeneity of learners;
 - use new learning methods;
 - make the most of new technologies.

(2) As stated in the Riga conclusions (2015).

Just released!

Focus: NEETs teachers in VET programmes

Research questions:

- What is the NEETs teachers' profile outline?
- What CPD needs for NEETs teachers?
- What teaching methods do NEETs teachers use in VET?
- How do NEETs teachers motivate their students and make VET programmes more relevant to the labour market?

Methodology: Questionnaire and interviews

Working paper series
No 24/MARCH 2025

THE PROFILE OF NEETS TEACHERS IN GREECE: FROM EUROPEAN POLICIES AND PRACTICES TO EMPIRICAL FINDINGS

Anthie Kyriakopoulou

14%

NEETs aged
15-29 in 2024

Source: [Cedefop, 2025](#)

NEETs teachers' profile

70% women
30% men

Average age
45 years old

More years of
experience as adult
educators than with
NEETs

Source: [Cedefop, 2025](#)

NEETs teachers need specialised training

Are **NOT** aware of the psychosocial characteristics of NEETs

45%

Have attended CPD activities on NEETs

Source: [Cedefop, 2025](#)

NEETs teachers: key actors in motivating NEETs

Source: [Cedefop, 2025](#)

83%

Believe **NEETs** teachers play a key role in motivating NEETs to pursue learning

74%

Say **NEETs' motivation** is 'completely' or 'very much' linked to **completing VET** programmes

NEETs teachers: making VET programmes more relevant to the labour market

Believe NEETs teachers play a role in aligning VET programmes with labour market needs

NEETs teachers collaborate with company specialists

Source: [Cedefop, 2025](#)

Key take aways

Experience matters most
more direct experience working
with NEETs
→ better prepared

Targeted CPD is essential
focused on NEETs characteristics

Need for extended support

- psychosocial
- language mediation

Investing in hands-on experience
yields the greatest impact

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Why upscale research on NEETs teachers?

- 1 Build a stronger evidence base:** better understand teachers' profiles, CPD needs and challenges
- 2 Identify and share good practices:** support mutual learning and effective transfer of what works
- 3 Creating comprehensive support systems:** liaise teachers with career guidance practitioners, psychologists, social workers, employers, in-company trainers
- 4 Drive coordinated, impact-oriented policy:** mobilise resources, coordinate stakeholders and tailor CPD to real needs

We listen to teachers' voices

The European Vocational Teacher Survey 2025-2026

Supporting teachers in VET schools

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SHAPING LEARNING AND SKILLS FOR EUROPE

Fourth Policy learning forum

Launching the European Vocational Teacher Survey (EVTS)

25-26 September 2025

Hybrid event

#VETTeachersTrainers

#VETtoolkit

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Thank you Any Questions?

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Thank you for your participation

23 June 2025
10.00-13.30 CET
Brussels

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